

Species 1: *H. pachinus*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.39; high PNT

NOT test

Species 2: *H. cydno*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.61; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red=S1>S2, Blue=S1<S2, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.408

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
D= 0.114

D
p.value = 0.22555

Background 2->1

D
p.value = 0.12635

Background 1->2

D
p.value = 0.01136

Species 1: *H. pachinus*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.41; high PNT

NDT test

Species 2: *H. cydno*

PC1, PNT.index: 0.78; high PNT

Environmental overlap

PC1
Red= $S1 > S2$, Blue= $S1 < S2$, Cor. Uncorrected= 0.493

Equivalency

Niche Similarity:
 $D = 0.158$

Background 2→1

D
p.value = 0.03571

Background 1→2

D
p.value = 0.01316